

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Average % inhibition (Concentration in ppm)								
	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>			<i>Curvularia lunata</i>			<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>		
	100	50	20	100	50	20	100	50	20
DISHNBA	30 44	20 52	11 72	38 64	25 73	14 34	32 70	21 92	12 84
Mn(DISHNBA) ₂	25 62	16 70	7 68	27 46	17 72	9 22	25 98	17 08	8 64
Fe(DISHNBA) ₂	25 50	16 54	7 52	27 20	17 50	9 08	25 80	16 86	8 50
Co(DISHNBA) ₂	25 80	16 88	7 94	27 68	18 04	9 48	26 70	17 32	8 86
Ni(DISHNBA) ₂	25 86	16 96	8 02	27 82	18 20	9 60	26 82	17 44	8 98
Cu(DISHNBA) ₂	26 02	17 14	8 24	28 58	18 76	10 12	27 14	17 84	9 22
DISHOBA	32 56	21 63	13 04	41 57	27 12	15 02	35 46	24 23	14 78
Mn(DISHOBA) ₂	26 42	16 94	8 20	30 95	18 64	9 78	26 49	17 84	9 37
Fe(DISHOBA) ₂	26 10	16 60	7 46	30 42	18 10	9 40	26 20	17 12	9 06
Co(DISHOBA) ₂	26 92	17 23	8 78	31 62	19 25	10 24	27 12	18 49	9 80
Ni(DISHOBA) ₂	27 14	17 41	8 94	31 78	19 32	10 35	27 30	18 85	9 88
Cu(DISHOBA) ₂	27 92	18 12	9 35	32 24	19 98	10 78	27 88	19 20	10 46
MPSHNBA	30 36	39 26	22 46	74 86	38 35	21 95	70 24	36 22	22 24
Mn(MPSHNBA) ₂	36 26	23 24	12 78	35 96	20 76	12 24	33 78	22 84	12 86
Fe(MPSHNBA) ₂	35 87	20 84	12 12	34 24	20 12	11 80	32 78	22 00	12 00
Co(MPSHNBA) ₂	39 02	24 22	13 62	37 02	22 79	13 86	34 60	23 30	13 30
Ni(MPSHNBA) ₂	39 20	24 40	13 84	37 12	23 06	13 62	34 89	23 42	13 42
Cu(MPSHNBA) ₂	40 84	25 87	14 79	38 54	24 12	14 14	35 76	24 02	14 02
MPSHOBA	34 68	41 54	24 32	79 23	40 67	23 56	75 46	40 02	23 12
Mn(MPSHOBA) ₂	38 57	24 78	13 24	37 82	23.46	13 12	35 80	23.00	13 20
Fe(MPSHOBA) ₂	38 12	24 23	12 95	37 46	22 98	12 81	35 44	22 12	12 78
Co(MPSHOBA) ₂	39 43	24 45	13 78	38 12	24 04	13 97	36 05	23 78	14 00
Ni(MPSHOBA) ₂	39 70	24 60	14 12	38 40	24 12	14 11	36 18	23 94	14 25
Cu(MPSHOBA) ₂	41 52	26 02	15 06	39 95	24 97	14 87	37 26	24 46	14 93

*Abbr same as in Table 1.

using Czapeck's Dox agar medium. Percentage inhibition¹⁶ was calculated (after 168 h).

The fungicidal screening data are presented in Table 2. The Schiff bases were found to be more fungitoxic than the metal complexes. The fungicidal activity showed a gradual change with change of metal ion in the complexes and revealed the order, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$. Thus the Fe^{III} complexes were found to be least toxic while the Cu^{II} complexes showed maximum fungitoxicity. Generally, Schiff bases containing chloro group were found to be more fungitoxic than those containing nitro group. However, all the Schiff bases and their metal complexes were found to be fungitoxic although in varied degrees.

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Polarographic Behaviour of DDD and BHC in Aqueous Mixtures of Organic Solvents and in Presence of some Ionic and Non-ionic Surfactants vis-a-vis Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of DDD and BHC in aqueous mixtures of inert organic solvents and in the presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants vis-a-vis kinetics of

the electrode reaction has not been studied so far. Hence the title study has been undertaken in aqueous mixtures of ethanol, propanol, butanol and dimethyl formamide and also in presence of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants.

Experimental

DDD and BHC (Hindustan Insecticides) were recrystallised from acetone before use. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The concentration of each depolariser was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} and 5.0×10^{-4} M respectively. Desired concentration of various constituents of BR buffer of pH 7 were added to the solutions to be polarographed. Tetramethylammonium bromide (TMAB; 0.1 M) was used as a supporting electrolyte. A Toshniwal CL 02 polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL 50 polyflex galvanometer was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction of DDD and BHC was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon¹. The value of n was found to be 4 and 6 for DDD and BHC respectively at pH 7. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient of DDD and BHC in the presence of aqueous mixtures of organic solvents and in presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. The potential-dependent rate constant $k_{t,h}$ was calculated by Koutecky method^{2,3}. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{t,h}^2$) were calculated⁴ from the plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{a,a.}$. Throughout the measurement the current at the end of the drop (i.e., the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites⁵. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m = 2.8 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 3.0 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.357 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$ and $h_{\text{corr}} = 43.4 \text{ cm}$.

Aqueous mixtures of the following organic solvents were used: ethanol, propanol, butanol and dimethylformamide (DMF).

The various ionic and non-ionic surfactants used in the present study were as follows: cationic, lauryl pyridinium chloride (LPC) and cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC); anionic, sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) and dodecyl benzene sulphate (DBS); and non-ionic, gelatin and Triton X-100.

Results and Discussion

Both DDD and BHC give two well-defined diffusion-controlled waves in presence of increasing amount of organic solvents (50–80%, v/v) and ionic and non-ionic surfactants (1×10^{-4} – $1 \times 10^{-3}\%$) at pH 7. Each reduction step of DDD corresponds to a two-electron reduction process, while in the case of BHC the first step corresponds to a two-electron process and the second one to a four-electron process. Thus, in the overall reduction process of DDD, four electrons are involved while in case

of BHC six-electrons are involved. Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of DDD and BHC in presence of increasing percentage of organic solvents as well as in presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants were applied. The slope values of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical values expected for a two-electron and four-electron reversible reduction processes. From this it follows that the polarographic reduction of DDD and BHC in different steps is irreversible^{6b}. Further, the theory of irreversible waves^{6,7} predicts that the current is independent of the pressure-head of mercury at the foot of the wave and becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$. This dependence of the current on h_{corr} at different stages of the wave was also studied and it was found that the current was independent of h_{corr} at the foot of the wave, whereas it was proportional to $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave thereby confirming the irreversible nature of the wave.

The viscosity of the experimental solutions was also measured as a function of the percentage of organic solvent/ionic and non-ionic surfactants. The inconstancy of the product $i_d \eta^{1/2}$ indicates⁸ a change in the effective size of the diffusing molecules of DDD and BHC caused by changes in the degree of solvation (hydration) of these depolarisers. Consequently, their diffusion coefficients decrease with the increasing amounts of the organic solvent/ionic and non-ionic surfactants.

Since the plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{a,a.}$ in the presence of aqueous mixtures of different organic solvents and also in presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants are linear, there is only one rate-determining step^{9,10} involved in the electroreduction of each depolariser. The influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents and surfactants on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reactions of DDD and BHC is discussed below in terms of the values of the kinetic parameters.

αn_a values: A perusal of the values of αn_a shows that they decrease with increasing amounts of all the organic solvents and surfactants used in the present study. The values of αn_a lie in the range 0.28–0.50 in presence of aqueous mixtures of different organic solvents as well as in presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. An attempt to estimate n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step, apparently leads to a conclusion^{10,11} that n_a is equal to 1 because for a totally irreversible systems, as the present ones, α should be less than¹² 0.5. Since the decrease in the values of αn_a is indiscrete and no two consecutive values differ by a factor of two, the decrease in the values of αn_a due to a change in n_a may be ruled out. Thus, it is α which is decreasing with the increase in the percentage of organic solvents and with increasing amounts of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. A decrease in the value of α thus implies that the transfer of electron is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode

reactions of DDD and BHC are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing amounts of organic solvents and ionic and non-ionic surfactants.

$k_{r,h}^0$ values: A perusal of the values of $k_{r,h}^0$ shows that there is no regularity in the variation of $k_{r,h}^0$ values with the increasing amounts of organic solvents and ionic and non-ionic surfactants. Meites^{5a} also hinted at the limitation of $k_{r,h}^0$ in interpreting the results. However, the influence of increasing amounts of organic solvents and ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the electrode reactions of DDD and BHC can be studied^{1a-1c} in terms of the value of the potential-dependent rate constant ($k_{r,h}$) at a suitable potential which should be such as to lie between the potential corresponding to the foot and the plateau of the polarographic wave. At such a potential both the rate of the electron-transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. The values of $k_{r,h}$ at such a potential (for the I step of BHC this potential is -0.40 V while for the II one this is -1.26 V; for the I step of DDD this potential is -0.50 V and for the II step this is -1.30 V vs SCE) have been obtained. From these values it is seen that the parameter $k_{r,h}$ at such a potential decreases with increasing amounts of organic solvents and also with increasing amounts of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. This shows that the irreversible electrode reactions of DDD and BHC are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of organic solvents and surfactants. A decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing amounts of organic solvents and surfactants support this conclusion.

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Application of *ortho*-Lithiation Reaction. Synthesis of some 3-Ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins

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VARIOUS 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins bearing an alkyl group at C-3 with oxygenation on aromatic ring occur in nature. Literature survey reveals that there are very few reports for the synthesis of such compounds¹⁻³. Hence, an investigation on the synthesis of some 3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins has been carried out using *ortho*-lithiation on carboxamide followed by alkylation with an epoxide^{4,5}.

1

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- 1,2 a; $R_1 = \text{OMe}, R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$
 b; $R_2 = \text{OMe}, R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$
 c; $R_4 = \text{OMe}, R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 d; $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = \text{H}, R_3 = \text{Me}$
 e; $R_2 = \text{Me}, R_1 = R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$
 f; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OMe}, R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$

Substituted-*N*-methylbenzamides (1a-f) were lithiated with *n*-BuLi at room temperature under inert atmosphere and the resultant *ortho*-lithio derivatives were subjected to alkylation with 1,2-butylene oxide. Alkaline hydrolysis and usual work up⁶ afforded 3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (2a-f) which were characterised by analytical, ir and pmr spectral data (Table 1).

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer. Solid compounds were crystallised from ether-hexane.

N-Methylbenzamides (1a-f): *m*-Methoxy-(1a, m.p. 65°), *p*-methoxy-(1b, m.p. 120°), *o*-methoxy-(1c, b.p. 147–48°/2 mm), *m*-methyl-(1d, b.p. 178–80°), *p*-methyl-(1e, m.p. 146°) and 3,4-dimethoxy-(1f, m.p. 127°)-*N*-methylbenzamides were prepared by the action of $\text{SOCl}_2/\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ on the corresponding aromatic acids.

Lithiation of N-methylbenzamides (1a-f) and alkylation of ortho-lithioderivatives with 1,2-butylene oxide. General procedure: To a well-stirred solution of *N*-methylbenzamide (1a-f; 5 g) in dry THF (75 ml, freshly distilled over LiAlH_4) was added at room temperature *n*-BuLi (0.128 mol) in